

STUDY OF THE PROCESS OF PURIFICATION OF ZINC SULFATE SOLUTIONS FROM IMPURITIES

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Abstract. *The article describes the procedure for removing different contaminants via sulfate of zinc solution, including iron, copper, and cadmium ions in detail. Studies have been conducted on the use of zinc dust in the application of acid sulfuric to the concentration of zinc solution. The effect of the ratio of metals and zinc powder (Me:CP) on it is reported what the liquid phase's makeup of chemicals stands. It has been found that an increase in the percentage of zinc powder significantly reduces the amount of copper and cadmium ions in the solution, without significantly affecting the iron content. Ammonia was used to remove iron from the solution, which made it possible to achieve a high degree of purification with an optimal iron ratio of 1:1.05. The experimental results have shown that correctly selected conditions ensure iron removal with an efficiency of up to 98.1%, while the composition of the other components remains virtually unchanged. Thus, the methods developed for purifying zinc sulfate solutions make it possible to obtain high-purity solutions suitable for further industrial use in the production of zinc sulfate.*

Keywords: *zinc sulfate, solution purification, zinc dust, copper ions, cadmium ions, sulfate ions, iron, ammonia, coagulation, filtration.*

INTRODUCTION

Eliminating different contaminants from zinc sulfate solutions is of crucial importance in the production of zinc and its derivatives. Copper, cadmium, and sulfate ions in the liquid phase can have a deleterious effect on the finished product's quality and diminish the efficiency of technological processes. Therefore, the development of effective methods for removing these impurities is an important task for the chemical and metallurgical industries [1].

The article presents information on zinc compounds, its parts, the importance of zinc sulfate and some of its parts, and production volumes. The production and laboratory method for obtaining zinc sulfate are described. Crystalline zinc sulfate is a product for processing sulphuric acid and zinc concentrate, followed by the creation of the final product [1].

The prospect of decreasing the ratio Me:Zinc powder=1:(1.05-1.10), or the quantity of copper in the liquid phase, from 0.26% to 0.01% is provided. Lowering the copper concentration from 0.53% to 0.01% is possible by ammonization of the copper-refined solution in the Fe:NH₃=1:1.1 ratio. In the process of turning zinc concentrate into sulfuric acid, empirical equations are derived to determine the impact of temperature, the Zn:H₂SO₄ ratio, and the length of the operation on the pulp's density and viscosity [2].

Integrated waste processing eliminates long-term storage of zinc film, reduces costs for disinfection and decontamination of waste solutions, and reduces environmental pollution with toxic compounds of non-ferrous metals [3].

The most important methods for obtaining ZnO with metallurgical and chemical methods are presented [4].

Using modern equipment and analytical methods, the zinc preservative concentrate was analyzed and its complete chemical composition was determined [5].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study aims to investigate the cleaning procedure for zinc sulfate solutions from copper, cadmium and iron ion impurities using zinc dust, as well as to study the method of iron removal using ammonia. As part of the work, experiments were conducted on the sulfuric acid treatment of zinc concentrate combined with the addition of zinc dust and ammonia, which made it possible to determine the optimal conditions for achieving a high degree of purification.

Studies were carried out to lessen the amount of copper, cadmium, and sulfate ions in the liquid phase because of their presence in the liquid phase adding zinc dust when processing zinc concentrate with sulfuric acid.

The information on how the ratio of Me to zinc dust (ZD) affects the liquid phase's chemical makeup is provided below, by applying a 30% sulfuric acid solution to zinc concentrate and calcining it at 900°C in a Zn:H₂SO₄ ratio from 1:0.8 to 1:1.1 (Table 1).

Table 1. The influence of the Zn:H₂SO₄ and Me:CP ratio on the composition of the phase of liquid

No.	Me:CP	The liquid phase's chemical makeup, mass %				
		Zn	Cu	Cd	SO ₄ ²⁻	H ₂ O
1	1:0.0 1:0.0	14.88	0.26	0.13	26.39	60.61
2	1:0.8 1:0.8	14.88	0.19	0.07	26.24	59.50
3	1:1.0 1:1.0	14.88	0.10	0.001	26.10	58.30
4	1:1.05 1:1.05	14.88	0.0008	0.0004	25.96	57.03
5	1:1.1 1:1.1	14.88	0.0008	0.0004	25.96	57.03

*The Me:CP ratio varied from 1:0.8 to 1:1.1.

The results collected demonstrate that the fluid phase's copper concentration drops about 0.26% to 0.0008% as the amount of zinc dust increases in the absence of the addition of CP also at a ratio of Me:CP=1:(1.05-1.1), cadmium from 0.13% to 0.0004%, SO₄²⁻ from 26.39% to 25.96%.

The iron concentration of the zinc sulfide solvent is not much changed by the addition of CP. Thus, ammonia was used to separate the zinc sulfate solutions from iron.

The established technique shifts the protolytic equilibrium from left to right, forming iron in the form of Fe(OH)₂ (II) from diluted acidified solutions:

After that, the colloidal solution was left to coagulate. This was followed by filtration. After washing with ammonium nitrate solution, it was calcined and dried at 800°C. Fe₂O₃ served as a weight form. Incorrect calcination conditions or excessive temperatures resulted in a decrease in the weight of the deposit and, as a consequence, in underestimating the results. This may cause some iron to be reduced to the divalent species (6Fe₂O₃ = 4Fe₃O₄ + O₂).

Interestingly, the precipitation process does not require the presence of ions that form precipitates and bind iron (III) into soluble complexes, such as glycerol, sugars, tartaric and citric

acids, phosphate, arsenate, vanadate, and silicate ions. Additionally, a variety of contaminants, such as cobalt and sulfate ions, are absorbed by this silt with the surface formed. Determining which ions generate hydroxides that are insoluble in ammonia is also undesirable, such as Cr^{3+} , Al^{3+} , etc.

Figure 1 shows zinc sulfate solutions made from iron produced from zinc concentrate calcined at 900°C in a ratio of $\text{Zn}:\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 1:1.05$, with a sulfuric acid concentration of 30% and a process duration of 90 minutes. The impact of the stoichiometric ratio $\text{Fe}:\text{NH}_3$ on the degree of purification of these solutions is examined.

Fig. 1. Effect of $\text{Fe}:\text{NH}_3$ ratio in iron removal from sulfate of zinc solve

Reduced iron in the solution from 0.53% to 0.01% is the outcome of raising the $\text{Fe}:\text{NH}_3$ ratio from 1:0.0 to 1:1.1. Consequently, the amount of iron precipitation rises to 98.1% while the other constituents' contents essentially remain the same. In a 1:1 / 1:1 ratio, free acid content is essentially nonexistent.

The $\text{Fe}:\text{NH}_3$ ratio = 1:1.05 is the optimal condition for the liquid phase iron removal process. The degree of iron removal from the solution is 98.1%, and its content in the solution does not exceed 0.01%.

As a result, research on the removal of contaminants from zinc sulfate solutions has demonstrated the potential for producing a pure zinc sulfate solution for use in a variety of industrial applications.

CONCLUSION

Accompanying contaminants taint the zinc sulfate solutions made from the Khandiz Zn concentration. Zinc dust was introduced to reduce the zinc sulfate, cadmium, and copper content in the solution. It is observed that with an increase in the amount of zinc dust, the Cu content in the phase of fluid decreases by 0.26% to 0.0008% with a ratio of $\text{Me}:\text{CP} = 1: (1.05-1.1)$, cadmium from 0.13% to 0.0004%, SO_4^{-2} from 26.39% to 25.96%.

In the zinc sulfate solution, the addition of CP has virtually no effect on the iron content. Based on this, using ammonia, ZnSO_4 solution was separated from Fe.

A ratio $\text{Fe}:\text{NH}_3 = 1: 1.05$ is the ideal circumstances for removing Fe from the liquid phase. Under these circumstances, the solution's iron concentration is kept to a minimum of 0.01% and its degree of purification from iron is 98.1%.

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